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Water Body Name: SALIM ALI LAKE, AURANGABAD

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Abstract

Water bodies play a critical role in the development of urban spaces. They have diverse functions including domestic purposes, wastewater dilution, ecological services, green space management, biodiversity and temperature regulation. However, they have currently become merely a sink for solid waste and wastewater. Deteriorating infrastructure and encroachments also continue to threaten the health of water bodies.

There is no doubt that the momentum towards restoring and rejuvenating our water bodies is building up. The Government of India (GoI) has put Water Bodies in focus by creating the new Mission Amrit Sarovar Jal Dharohar Sanrakshan campaign which is a mission to focus on rejuvenation of various water bodies within the country.

Salim Ali Lake is a historical lake in Aurangabad city of Maharashtra, and has strategic location to tourist similar to park and being visited by families and people. The lake surrounds with good flora providing habitat to a variety of fauna. The lake is being surrounded by residential colonies and which is acting as an important source of sewage in it. The lake water is greenish in colour; this means that lake water is contaminated.

In this project we have studied about the history and geographical conditions of lake along with its hydrology. Spatiotemporal Analysis was done in order to find the variations in lake with respect to time. Also the water quality parameters were tested to know the factors contributing to the pollution in lake. After visiting the lake and studying the above factors some measures are suggested for rejuvenation and conservation of lake.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background:

Aurangabad is the historic city from Maharashtra and presently it is identified as one of the industrial developed places of Maharashtra. It is located in between latitude 19° 53' North and a longitude 75° 20' East (Boralkar, 2012). The city area is expanding at rapid rate developing the building complexes and realizing higher quantity of sewage and other kinds of waste in surrounding urban environment. This Salim Ali Lake is one of the most important surface water resources, which providing the habitat to many animals and to plants. Specifically, it acts as good habitat for many kinds of migratory birds. Every year in past good numbers of migratory birds were visited water body as the water quality was good (Patil et al., 2007). But from last few years say for ten to fifteen years the number of migratory birds has been reduced significantly. Therefore there is a need to study the habitat component of Salim Ali Lake is necessary. Hence the present work of study of water quality of Salim Ali Lake was undertaken during the winter season. In past two to three decade the Salim Ali Lake has provided the water to the people for domestic use. The people have used water body for various purposes. It has been used for recreational purpose also. The people living in vicinity of lake are being using the water of this lake for domestic and non-domestic purposes like washing cattle's and vehicles, swimming, etc. such activities are responsible for changing the physicochemical parameters and may increase hardness (Banejad and Abdo salehi, 2009). The grey water from lake has been used by man for domestic purposes.

Fig No. 1: Ariel view of Salim Ali Lake

The waste water generated from houses and residential areas around the lake is being directly disposing in the lake. The increased residential colonies around the Salim Ali Lake during the past one to two decades are disposing the waste in higher quantities. The increased input of sewage might responsible for degrading the aquatic habitat. The contaminants promoting the microorganism's growth in it and organic matters making water deficient of oxygen. The contaminated water may provide habitat to vector species (Mara, 1974). Many of diseases transfer from the insects like mosquito and flies to the human. Organic matter may lead to decrease the dissolved oxygen in the water and which may affect the aquatic organisms like fish, fauna Therefore there is a need of protection water quality of Salim Ali Lake in good condition. As indiscriminate human development around the lake is going on, this is degrading the water quality at rapid rate. Therefore, to know the present status of water quality the work has been undertaken and determined the water quality in terms of its physicochemical parameters. The nature loving society and the governmental officials may want to reduce the degree of contamination of surface water like lakes, rivers, ponds, dams and seas (Pandey and Tiwari, 2009) and for which they must understood first the existing quality of water resource. To reduce the disposal of any kind of waste and pollutants in to the surface water, there is a need of detail understanding of specific source of pollutant (Mohammed and Gupta, 2009). By reducing the input of contaminants from such sources one can keep the water body clean and suitable water quality for domestic use purposes. It is frequently observed that the domestic animals are washing in the lakes or in ponds and in river water. Those are using such water body for drinking purpose also. Therefore, there is a need of assessment of water quality of surface water body (Kelein, 1959).

Fig no. 2: Location of lake

1.2 Objectives

- To examine the lake.
- To study different process of rejuvenation
- To study the scope for further development in the surrounding after rejuvenation of the lake.

2. Hydrology of the Lake

Fig No. 3: Land use of Salim Ali Lake

Description:

The formation of hydrology in Salim Ali Lake is natural as well as artificially designed.

As for natural formation the Prehistoric Magma eruption in Deccan plateau lead to the formation of basalt dyke.

This basalt deck act as barrier as its physical properties is impermeable. The natural drainage of ground water is also coordinating with basalt dyke brigade which leads to natural catchment area as shown in figure below.

Hydrology of Salim Ali Lake

- The portion above the dyke forms the catchment of the Salim Ali Lake.
- Then from the lake outlet water flows through drainage tunnels beneath the Himayat Bagh which later meets the Kamal Talab.

Fig No. 4: Watershed of Salim Ali Lake

Fig No. 5: catchment area of Salim Ali Lake

3. Spatiotemporal Analysis:

2003

2005

2008

2011

2012

2014

2016

2017

2018

2019

2020

2021

The above satellite images show the spatial variation of the lake from the year 2003 to 2021. From the spatiotemporal variations it can be observed that there is an uncontrolled growth of unwanted vegetation such as weeds and plants from the year 2012. These unwanted weeds lead to various problems such as

- Interfere with or prohibit recreational activities such as fishing, and boating.
- Detract from the aesthetic appeal of a body of water.

- Fish kills due to removal of too much oxygen from the water. Oxygen depletion occurs when plants die and decompose. Photosynthetic production of oxygen ceases, and the bacteria, which break down the plant material, use oxygen in their own respiration. Fish kills in summer are frequently caused by die-offs of algae blooms.
- Produce quiet water areas that are ideal for mosquito breeding.
- Certain algae can give water bad tastes and odours.

Also it can be observed that a layer of eutrophication appearing from the year 2011 which is gradually expanding annually and has covered a large portion till the year 2021. Eutrophication leads to Deterioration of Water Quality, Degradation of Recreational Opportunities and destruction of benthic habitat by shading of submerged vegetation.

In addition to this there is annual variation in water level of the water body.

4. Water Testing Parameter

4.1 Sample collection

Samples were collected from the water body at three different locations as shown in the image.

Fig No. 5: Collection of Water Sample

Fig no. 6: Points of water sample collection

4.2 Testing of Water sample

1. pH

pH is an indicator of acidity or alkalinity. pH is a logarithmic scale and an increase or decrease of one pH unit is a 10 fold change. Neutral water has a pH of 7, acidic solutions have values between 0 - 6 and alkaline solutions have values between 8-14.

Procedure:

- 1) Take 10 ml of water sample to be tested in the test jar.
- 2) Add 10 drops of pH1. Mix well.
- 3) Now place this test jar with different colours.
- 4) View from topside and observed the colour.
- 5) Arrive at the appropriate reading by moving the test jar from one concentration to another.
- 6) Match the correct colour and read pH reading from the colour chart.

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	8.5	6 – 8
Sample 2	8.5	
Sample 3	8.5	

2. Nitrate

Procedure:

- 1) Take 5ml of sample in the test tube provided.
- 2) Now add 1 spoonful of HNT1. Shake well. Keep for 10 minutes, while shaking intermittently.
- 3) To this now add 3 drops of HNT2. Mix well. Keep for 3 minutes, while shaking intermittently.
- 4) Now add 1 spoonful of HNT3. Shake well. Wait for 5 minutes to allow maximum colour development. Dilute to 25 ml mark with DM water or Nitrate free water.
- 5) Transfer the content in small comparator tube provided here.
- 6) Read the PPM as follows.
 - a) Place the comparator tube on the small inner (white) circle on the colour comparison chart.

- b) View from the top of the comparator tube to compare the sample colour and colour around.
- c) Match the colours by moving the tube from one circle to another. d) Read the PPM Nitrate after arriving at the correct match.

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	1 PPM	0 – 40 PPM
Sample 2	1 PPM	
Sample 3	1 PPM	

Fig no. 7: Nitrate testing

3. Fluoride

Procedure:

- 1) Take 10 ml of water sample to be tested in the test jar.
- 2) Add one drops of "FD1" and mix well. If a yellow colour does not appear, then add "FD2A" till you get yellow colour.
- 3) Now add "FD2B" till the solution become colourless. Add 8 more drops of FD2B.
- 4) Add 2 spoonful "FD3". Mix well to dissolve.
- 5) Now drop wise add "FD4 counting the number of drops while mixing, until the colour changes from yellow to the first distinct pink colour.

Note: If the expected Fluoride of sample is more than 2 PPM, then use "FD5" Instead of "FD4".

Calculations:

Fluoride as PPM Fluonde = $0.2X$ (Number of drops of "FD4")

= $0.5X$ (Number of drops of "FD5")

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	1.6 PPM	0 – 5 PPM
Sample 2	2 PPM	
Sample 3	1.6 PPM	

Fig No.8: Fluoride testing

4. Total Hardness

Procedure:

- 1) Take 10 ml of water sample to be tested in the test jar.
- 2) Add one spoonful of "TH 1".
- 3) Mix contents well to dissolve.
- 4) Add 10-12 drops of "TH 2" and mix contents well.
- 5) Now drop wise add "TH 5" counting the number of drops while mixing, until the colour changes from red to blue.

Calculations :

Total Hardness as PPM CaCO_3 = $25 X$ (Number of drops of "TH 5")

25-500 ppm Total Hardness

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	125 PPM	60 – 150 PPM
Sample 2	225 PPM	
Sample 3	175 PPM	

5. Alkalinity**Procedure:**

- 1) Take 10 ml of water sample to be tested in the test jar.
- 2) Add 2 drops of "AK1" and mix well.
- 3) If a pink colour appears it indicates presence of P Alkalinity.
- 4) Then drop wise add "AK2" counting the number of drops while mixing, until the pink colour disappears (N Drops)
- 5) To this solution add one spoonful of "AK4" .The sample will turn green.
- 6) Now drop wise add "AK2" counting the number of drops while mixing, until the colour changes from green to reddish violet (N1 Drops).

Note: If expected Alkalinity is more than 200 ppm, then use "AK3" instead of "AK2"

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	140 PPM	20 - 200 PPM
Sample 2	170 PPM	
Sample 3	150 PPM	

6. Chloride

Chlorides: The presence of chlorides in natural waters can mainly be attributed to dissolution of salt deposits in the form of ions (Cl). Otherwise, high concentrations may indicate pollution by sewage, industrial wastes, intrusion of seawater or other saline water. It is the major form of inorganic

anions in water for aquatic life. High chloride content has a deleterious effect on metallic pipes and structures, as well as agricultural plants.

Procedure:

- 1) Take 10 ml of water sample to be tested in the test jar.
- 2) Add one spoonful of CD1.
- 3) Mix contents well to dissolve.
- 4) Add CD2 drop wise till the sample turns yellow.
- 5) Now drop wise add CD3 counting the number of drops while mixing, until the colour changes from yellow to bluish violet.

Note: If the expected Chloride of the sample is more than 200 PPM, then use CD4 instead of CD3.

Calculations: Chloride as PPM Chloride

$$= 10 X (\text{Number of drops of CD3})$$

$$= 50X (\text{Number of drops of CD4})$$

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	90 PPM	1 - 100 PPM
Sample 2	80 PPM	
Sample 3	90 PPM	

7. Turbidity

Turbidity is a measure of degree at which the water loses its transparency because of the presence of suspended particles. The amount of total suspended solids in the water is high, then that water sample has higher turbidity. There hardness are various parameters influencing the turbidity/cloudiness of the water such as algae growth, phytoplankton, sediments from erosion, waste discharge, and urban runoff.

Principle:

Turbidity is depended on the comparison of the intensity of light scattered by the sample under characterized conditions with the power of the light scattered by a standard reference suspension under similar conditions.

The turbidity of the sample is thus estimated from the amount of light scattered by the sample taking a reference with standard turbidity suspension. The higher the power of scattered light the more is the turbidity.

The water form Turbidity can be measured using either an electronic turbidity meter or a turbidity tube. Turbidity is usually measured in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU) or Jackson Turbidity Units (JTU), depending on the method used for measurement. The two units are roughly equal. JTU is measured with the Jackson candle turbidity meter. This unit is no longer used.

Apparatus:

Nephelometer, Nephelometer tube, Conical flask, Pipette, Beaker, Glass rod.

REAGENTS:

1. Distilled water
2. Stock turbidity solutions
 - a. Solution 1: Hydrazine Sulphate
 - b. Solution 2: Hexamethylenetetramine

Preparation of reagents:

1. Take Hydrazine Sulphate in a beaker and measure it to 1 gm using the weighing scale (Solution 1).
2. Add 100 ml distilled water to the beaker. Then stir it through glass rod.
3. Take Hexamethylenetetramine in a beaker and measure it to 10 gm using the weighing scale (Solution 2).
4. Add 100 ml distilled water to the beaker. Then stir it through glass rod.
5. Mix 5 ml of solution 1 & 5 ml of solution 2 in another conical flask and let it stand for at least 24 hours. Then add 90 ml distilled water, making it of 100 ml sample. Mix it thoroughly. The Standard 400 NTU solution ready.
6. For making standard 40 NTU solution, take 10 ml of mixed solution (as mentioned in step 5), and dilute it to 100 ml. The turbidity of this solution is 40 NTU.

Steps:

1. Power the Nephelometer by clicking on the power button and place the sample cell with distilled water in Nephelometer.
2. Fill distilled water sample in nephelometer tube and set the reading to zero by using the knobs provided for setting.
3. Now fill the standard solution of 40 NTU in nephelometer tube, and set reading to 40 NTU by adjusting Nephelometer reading to 40 NTU using calibration knobs.

- After calibration, now add water sample to be tested in the nephelometer tube and measure the reading.

Fig no.9: Turbidity testing

Observation table:

Turbidity	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	50 NTU	0-10 PPM
Sample 2	239 NTU	
Sample 3	211 NTU	

Consequence of high turbidity:

The suspended solids in water absorb heat from the sunlight, making the temperature of turbid water higher and therefore reducing the concentration of O₂ in the water as oxygen dissolves better in lower temperature. The suspended solid in water scatter the light falling on it, thus decreasing the photosynthetic activity of plants and algae, which results in lower oxygen concentration in water. Therefore, particles settling to the bottom, shallow lakes fill in faster, fish eggs and insect larvae are covered and suffocated, gill structures get clogged or damaged.

Application of turbidity of water test data:

In water supply turbidity data information can be helpful to know the effectiveness and adequacy of the treatment delivered with various coagulants and the necessary doses.

The faulty operation of filter can be checked by estimating the turbidity of filtered water. The effective removal of suspended solids from the waste can be known from the measurements of wastewater turbidity.

To produce great quality effluent by using the least amount of chemical, the dose of the chemical can be adjusted or balanced by turbidity information.

Turbidity is an indicator of poor treatment plant efficiency, filter run timing, and contamination of distribution system and measurements of coagulants.

Turbidity standard:

As per IS 10500:2012 drinking water quality standards, acceptable limit for turbidity is 1 NTU, and permissible limit in the absence of alternate source is 5 NTU.

8. Dissolved Oxygen

Principle:

DO rapidly oxidizes the divalent manganous to its higher valency which forms a brown hydrated oxide precipitation after addition of NaOH and KI. In the presence of iodide ions in an acidic solution the oxidized manganese reverts the divalent state and liberates iodine from KI equivalent to the original DO content. The liberated iodine is then titrated against Sodium thiosulphate solution with starch as an indicator. $MnSO_4$ reacts with alkali to form white precipitate $Mn(OH)_2$ thus indicating absence of oxygen in the sample.

Apparatus:

BOD bottles (capacity 300 ml), burette, pipettes, conical flask, burette stands, tile, measuring cylinder, weight balance glass rod, beakers.

Reagents:

1. Winkler's A solution: Dissolve 48 gm tetra hydrate manganous sulphate in 100 ml distilled water. Filter if necessary.
2. Winkler's B solution: Dissolve 50 gm of NaOH and 15 gm of KI in 100 ml distilled water.
3. Starch indicator: Make a paste of 2gm LR grade soluble starch powder in distilled water. Pour this solution in 100 ml di water. Boil for few minutes. Cool the solution and then use.
4. Concentrated sulphuric acid
5. Standard sodium thiosulphate solution: Dissolve 24.82 gm $Na_2S_2O_3$ in distilled water and make up to 1 liter. It becomes 0.1N. Take 250 in solution and make up to 1 liter with distilled water to prepare 0.025N.

Procedure:

1. Collect the sample in 300ml BOD bottle.
2. Add 2 ml of Winkler's A solution and 2ml of Winkler's B solution well below the surface
3. Stopper immediately to remove air bubbles and mix carefully by inverting bottle up and down.
4. Allow the brown precipitate to settle down leaving clear supernatant.

5. Add conc. Sulphuric acid drop by drop till precipitate digested.
6. Rest topper the bottle and mix by inverting several times for complete dissolution.
7. A yellow colour solution appears.
8. Take 50 ml samples in conical flask.
9. Add few drops of starch indicator and titrate against 0.025N Na₂S₂O₃ solution.
10. Note down the reading until the colour changes from blue to colourless.

Fig no.10: DO testing

Observations:

1. In burette: 0.025 N sodium thiosulphate solution.
2. In conical flask: 50 ml sample + indicator.

CALCULATION:

$$DO(\text{mg / l}) = (V * 70) / u$$

Where,

V = ml of titrant used for DO determination (B.R.)

u = ml of water sample taken

70 = correction factor

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	0.84 PPM	Water body polluted below 4PPM
Sample 2	0.35 PPM	
Sample 3	0.42 PPM	

Result:

The amount of dissolved oxygen determined from the given sample is mg/l.

Environmental significance:

1. A minimum DO of 4 to 6mg / l is desirable for the survival of aquatic life; higher values of DO may cause corrosion of iron and steel.
2. High temperature, biological impurities, ammonia, nitrites, ferrous iron, chemicals such as hydrogen sulphide and organic matter reduces DO values.
3. Drinking water should be rich in DO for good taste.

Application of data:

1. It is necessary to know DO levels to assess the quality of raw water and to check on stream pollution.
2. DO test is basis for BOD test which is an important parameter to evaluate organic pollution potential of waste.
3. DO test is used to control oxygen in boiler feed water.
4. DO test is used to evaluate the pollution strength of domestic and industrial waste.
5. Determination of DO in waste water is useful to identify the nature of biochemical reactions whether aerobic anaerobic.

9. Total Dissolve Solids

Procedure:

1. Take 20 ml of water sample to be tested.
2. Click on the on button of electronic TDS metre.
3. The TDS meter is put into the water sample.
4. The reading is observed on the electronic screen on meter and notes it down.

Observation table:

Sample No.	Results	Permissible Range
Sample 1	423 PPM	0-500 PPM
Sample 2	414 PPM	
Sample 3	408 PPM	

5. Present Condition of Lake

▪ **Problems**

There are different problems at the lake perimeter which are as follows:

- i. Garbage disposal
- ii. Eutrophication
- iii. Broken fencing
- iv. Cultural immersion
- v. Plant growth
- vi. Inlet and outlet barriers

1. **Garbage disposal**

The large amount of garbage disposal was observed surrounding the lake and it leads to making it polluted. An open dump is an illegal waste disposal site and should not be confused with a permitted municipal solid waste landfill or a recycling facility. If allowed to remain, open dumps often grow larger, and may attract dumping of both solid and hazardous to water body and aquatic life.

Fig no. 11: Garbage disposal

2. **Eutrophication**

The layer of eutrophication, algae and mosses are observed along corners of the lake side. Harmful algal blooms, dead zones, and fish kills are the results of a process called eutrophication which occurs when the environment becomes enriched with nutrients, increasing the amount of plant and algae growth to estuaries and coastal waters.

Fig no. 12: Eutrophication at lake

3. Broken fencing

Fencing is broken around the lakeside allowing trespassers to contaminate it and increasing chances of casualties.

Fig no. 13: Broken fencing

4. Cultural immersion

It was seen from research papers that cultural intervention (garlands, flowers etc.) has caused pollution of lake.

Fig no. 14: Cultural immersion

5. Plant growth

Aquatic weeds and plants are causing severe intervene in DO of the lake. Uncontrolled growth of aquatic plants around the lake is taking place.

Fig no. 15: Plant growth

6. Inlet and outlet barriers

It was observed that no barriers or traps were provided at inlet and outlet sources causing the lake to contaminate with garbage.

Fig no. 16: Inlet and outlet barriers

6. Solutions to the Problems

▪ **Solutions**

1. Solution to garbage disposal
2. Solution to eutrophication
3. Solution to broken fencing
4. Solution to cultural immersion
5. Solution to Plant growth
6. Solution to inlet and outlet barriers

1. **Solution to garbage disposal**

1. Mesh/ nets to be installed surrounding the lake.
2. Installation of dustbins in surroundings
3. Appointing men for overlook

Fig no.17: Solution to garbage disposal

2. **Solution to eutrophication**

1. Reducing the contamination of lakes
2. Use of proper solutions and cleaning techniques

Fig no.18: Solution to eutrophication

3. Solution to broken fencing

1. Fencing should be made up of fine nets/ mesh
2. Height of the fence should be kept more.

Fig no.19: Solution to broken fencing

4. Solution to cultural immersion

Strict rules to be implemented for prohibition of cultural intervention.

5. Solution to Plant growth

1. Dweeding and Clearance of extra aquatic weed and plants.
2. Keeping necessary amount of weeds to maintain the phosphorous and nitrogen level in water.

6. Solution to inlet and outlet barriers

1. Barriers, net or mesh to be provided at inlet from STP and outlet sources.
2. Water should be treated properly at STP and after that should be transferred to lake

7. Rejuvenation of Lake

Rejuvenation is the process of rebuilding the old structure with new and advanced technology and with the good aesthetic view of the body for betterment of the area.

There are seven ways to rejuvenate fresh water in Salim Ali Lake are:

- 1) Boating
 - 2) Aeration fountain
 - 3) Fishing
 - 4) Solar street lights
 - 5) Seating Benches
 - 6) Bird houses
 - 7) Dustbins
1. **Boating:** Major tourist attraction is of boating. Re-starting the boating deck will lead to value increase of the lake. Also, it will help in water purification by the cycles of the moving boats. Both entertainment and maintenance of lake will be done if water boating will re-start.

Fig no.20: Boating

2. Aeration fountain: Due to the foul smell and lack of clean water boundaries aeration fountain filters should be added at the boundaries to reduce the problem of smell and filtration. This will keep the sludge away and aesthetic look of lake will be maintained.

The dissolved oxygen in the lake will be maintained and the water quality improved and it will help for the aquatic life of the lake.

Fig no.21: Aeration Fountain

3. Fishing:

Re-establishing fishes to enrich aquatic life is the only factor that will make a thousand birds return to this waterbody, true to its pristine name "Salim Ali Lake". All rejuvenation activities are incidental and supportive to it. However scientific fish farming and fishery management in city lakes did not receive due importance either in the DPR document or rejuvenation action priorities. Against the historical background of neglect of this factor and in the light of its relevance in the present context, this chapter discusses the issues highlighted by domain experts who have been consulted and based on the implementation process adopted in Salim Ali Lake. A balance is struck in the fish. farming and fishery management in urban lakes between ecological needs of stocking fish and allied species for optimizing societal economic benefits and to attract avian life.

Rejuvenation of most polluted urban lakes and conservation of the scarce freshwater resources assumed great significance and urgency from ecological, environmental, drinking water, and food points of view. People cannot live without clean water and pure

air. Aquatic life is the creator, promoter, and preserver of all this. Therefore, aquatic organisms get the first right on the water since they cannot survive without it. Among aquatic animals, fishes are the main source of food but hardly are we concerned about preserving them. It is needless to stress that fish plays a critical role in our food security and nutritional needs from time immemorial. Not merely that, no other developmental project serves the poorest of the poor, the fisher folk who depend on sustainable fishing in their traditional coracle. A rejuvenated urban lake helps in providing at doorstep clean water, an environment with pure air and quality fish. This is well appreciated by the citizens living in the neighbourhood of Salim Ali Lake after its rejuvenation. When the lakes are destroyed and turned unfit for fishing, these poor traditional families had to look elsewhere for livelihood. At least in rejuvenated lakes, they should be encouraged to return with their traditional skills.

The presence of native aquatic and avian life is accepted as the perfect barometer to measure the health of a lake without testing its water or soil qualities.

Fig no.22: Fishing

Rejuvenation should be done around the lake to make surrounding clean and visible by providing:

- 4. Street lights:** Street lights should surround the water body increasing its aesthetic value. For sustainable use street light with solar panels can be installed.

Fig no.23: Solar Street Lights

- 5. Seating benches:** Benches and wooden stools to be installed along the pathway so that the tourists will enjoy the scenic beauty of the lake and enjoy a leisure time.

Fig no.24: Seating Benches

- 6. Bird house:** As Salim Ali Lake is itself a home to many migratory species, it will be great idea to build bird houses alongside the lake. Leading to a conservation of biodiversity and maintaining the cycle of the nature.

Fig no.25: Bird house

7. **Dustbins:** Dustbins to be installed both inner and outer parts for litter control in the surrounding. Strict rules to be implemented if anyone found littering the area.

Fig no.26: Dustbins

8. Conservation of Lake

1. Conservation of plant life and species

All the economically important organisms should be identified and conserve it is important to conserve them and save them from getting extinct Maintain, restore, and increase ecological systems while promoting the implementation of better conservation practices

It involves the in-situ and ex-situ methods.

Fig no.27: Plant life

2. Conservation of the lake:

Water management, waste management and chemical treatments should be considered as the key components of conservation. Measures like cleaning of Water Body involving de-

silting, de-weeding, aeration, reduction of nutrient, removal of floating and other invasive aquatic plant-species or any successfully tested and technologically suitable to the local condition, may be taken up The shore-line of the Water Bodies should be properly fenced to protect it from encroachment.

Fig no. 28: lake view

3. Conservation of Birds and migratory Species:

Many bird species migrate to Salim Ali during winters. Keep feeders and bird baths clean to avoid disease and prevent mosquitoes from breeding. Plant Native plants provide food, nest sites, and cover for birds. Avoid Chemicals Birds may accidentally eat pesticide and herbicide pellets or prey that have been poisoned. This can kill a bird or have toxic effects on their own health and that of their growing embryos, including deformation or suppressed immune systems.

Fig no.29: Birds

4. Conservation of Infrastructure:

Maintaining infrastructure will reduce the no of casualties and fatality rates. Surrounding Gardens to be maintained and conserved increasing the aesthetic value of the lake. Promote sustainable infrastructure.

Fig no.30: Infrastructure

5. Conservation of aquatic life:

Aquatic Life is the crucial part of the lake conservation. Various types of fishes are found in the lake. Maintaining the lake quality aquatic life can be conserved. Limit Use of Plastics, Disposables and Single-Use Projects Part take in eco-tourism activities that support local communities Mind Your Carbon Footprint and Reduce Energy Consumption.

Fig no 31: Aquatic life